

Investigating the influence of online facilities on Students' Study Habits in computer studies in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Lois Folasayo Ajayi * and Mary Folasade Oyemomilara

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education, Ekiti State University, Ado Ekiti.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 26(02), 2276-2280

Publication history: Received on 02 April 2025; revised on 11 May 2025; accepted on 13 May 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.26.2.1816>

Abstract

The Internet influences many aspects of life, including the educational sector. The proliferation of online educational platforms has revolutionized student learning in the digital era. This study examined the influence of online facilities on students' study habits in Computer Studies in Ekiti state, Nigeria. This research aimed to examine the impact of online resources used for instruction on students' study habits in Computer Studies in secondary schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. To accomplish this objective, a null hypothesis was established to direct the research. A survey research design was adopted for the study. A sample of 85 respondents was drawn from a secondary school in Ekiti State for the study. A questionnaire designed by the researcher was the instrument used for data collection. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency count and percentages were used to answer the question raised, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation formula was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed no significant correlation between online facilities usage and study habits ($r = 0.0611$, $p = 0.5785$). The finding of the study revealed that online facilities has no significant influence on students' study habits in Computer Studies. Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that students should continue to employ any method and facility that is suitable for their study habits.

Keywords: Online facilities; Study habits; Secondary school; Computer Studies; Computer; Influence

1. Introduction

Education serves as a mechanism for imparting specific behaviors, regulations, values, skills, attitudes, and knowledge to individuals of all ages within a society, thereby providing them with vital resources for personal and societal advancement (Usman, Akinpelu, Akindoju, Fasinro, Onowugbeda, and Abanum, 2024). The primary objective of education is to convey wisdom and information throughout generations, therefore equipping youth to become responsible societal members and to sustain and advance society (Osuchukwu and Nebolise, 2019). The significance of education for the economic, social, and moral advancement of countries is paramount.

Today, teaching and learning have taken a new turn as a result of the integration of online facilities into the school learning environment. With the use of the various online facilities, students can easily interact with teachers as well as engage in various interactive sessions, using the available facilities. Educators are encouraged by the governments to adopt appropriate teaching methods, media, strategies, and techniques in the delivery of learning content to prepare learners for the outside world. The use of innovative teaching methods, techniques, or approaches in teaching and learning activities inside and outside the classroom has been observed to have a significant impact on students' study habits (Jazeel (2016).

The advantages of online facilities include worldwide connectivity, personalized learning, access to various learning materials, real-time information sharing; increased student engagement through interactive multimedia content, online

* Corresponding author: Lois Folasayo Ajayi

discussions, and collaborative projects; and reduced costs associated with traditional classroom-based learning. The disadvantages include technical issues, such as connectivity or network problems, poor video quality, and platform glitches; limit to opportunity for immediate feedback and interaction with instructors and peers; limit to social interaction and human connection, which are essential for emotional intelligence, empathy, and social skill; exposure of students to cyber security risks, such as data breaches, phishing scams, and malware attacks. Online facilities can make it challenging to assess and evaluate student learning, as instructors may not be able to observe students' work and study habits directly.

2. Literature Review

The use of online facilities in the field of education has provided students with enormous opportunities for easy access to various resources as well as information sharing. The internet has become a widely accepted channel for the exchange of information and networking. As a result, the dependence of students on the Internet is increasing rapidly day by day. Students basically use online facilities for academic as well as non-academic purposes. Lots of e-resources are available on the internet, which help students in enriching knowledge and study skills. The use of the Internet enhances the skills and capabilities of student which help them in their studies and in their professional life (Emeka and Nyeche, 2016)

Study habit refers to an adopted way and manner a student plans his or her private readings after classroom learning in order to attain mastery of a subject. It refers to the routines, practices, and strategies used by individuals to learn, retain, and recall information effectively. Nneji (2002) cited in Ogunjobi and Ogungbe (2016) describes study habits as learning tendencies that enable students to work privately. Study habits could vary among students based on their level and discipline. Students have been known to exhibit various study habits that work with each student differently, while most study habits though developed early in life are carried over to adulthood. Students with good study habits have tendencies that allow them to work out new ideas each day.

Study habits play an important role in determining academic success in the learning process. The success or failures of every student depend upon his/her study habits. Study is an art and as such it requires practice. Some students study more but they fail to achieve more (Singh and Sharma, 2022). The time spent on studying helps students retain the materials learned, which will eventually boost the students' performance outcomes during tests or examinations. Specifically, the study habits of students will determine how best they are likely to perform in a school subject. Students with ineffective study habits may end up receiving poor grades at school and this may easily distract, frustrate and create behavioural problems in them which may eventually make them dislike school and lead to them being unable to develop to their full potential (Aina, 2011).

Good study habits help students to achieve academic success, develop a growth mindset, and build confidence in their abilities. Good study habits include active learning, organization, time management, note-taking, review, and practice. Poor study habits could lead to academic difficulties such as examination malpractices and dropping out of school. Factors such as learning style, motivation, and environment can influence an individual's study habits. Singh and Sharma (2022) assert that study habit keeps students perfect in getting knowledge and developing attitudes towards things necessary for achievement in different fields of human endeavour. Good habit will reduce the wastage of energy and time.

Regarding the use of online resources, the digital age has revolutionized the way we learn, with a plethora of digital resources available at our fingertips. However, the quality and adequacy of these materials could have effect on learning experiences and outcomes. Scholars believe that students who used the library with up-to-date resources performed at a higher level than students in schools with minimal or no library resources (Ogungbe, 2005). In this age and time of technology, students find it easy to study with the use of online facilities and this is useful for students who may not find the library accessible due to distance or lack those confronted with the problem of obsolete materials. However, it should be worthwhile to investigate the impact of the use of online facilities on the study habits of students and how these are put to good effect or otherwise.

Lajwanti and Sharma (2013) investigated the effect of internet use on study habits and adjustment of higher secondary students and found significant differences in the mean of study habits and adjustment scores of internet users and non-users. Another study conducted by Momin (2014) on the relationship between internet usage and study habits of secondary school students revealed a significant negative relationship between study habits and internet use. Regarding the influence of the use of the internet on the study habits of students, the study result indicates that the learning habits of the internet users and non-users differed significantly and non-users of the internet were found to be better than internet users (Jazeel (2016). Joshi and Sharma (2017) examined the effect of internet usage on study habits of senior secondary students and found that internet nonusers have better study habits than the students who use the internet.

Keeping in view the analysis of the above reviews, it is expedient to conduct the present study to ascertain the influence of online facilities on secondary schools students' study habits in Computer Studies. This study aims at finding out the influence of online facilities on students' study habits in Computer Studies in secondary schools.

2.1. Purpose of the Study

This study aims to investigate how the use of online facilities for teaching influences students' study habits in Computer Studies.

2.2. Research Question

Do the students have access to online facilities for teaching Computer Studies?

2.3. Research Hypothesis

- H0: There is no significant influence of online facilities for teaching on students' study habits in Computer Studies.

3. Methodology

A descriptive survey design was used for the study. A purposive sampling technique was used to select the samples. The instrument used for data collection for this research work was a questionnaire. To improve the reliability and validity of the questionnaire, it was pre-tested on 20 randomly selected students in the school. The questionnaire was constructed based on the principal research questions for the investigation. 100 students offering Computer Studies were selected for Senior Secondary School Two (SSS II). 100 copies of the questionnaire were administered to SSS Two students. Out of the 100 copies of the questionnaire administered to the students, eighty-five (85) copies were properly filled, returned and used for data analysis.

3.1. Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using percentages and Pearson Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance.

4. Results

Table 1 Demographic Information

Gender	No of Students	%
Male	38	44.7
Female	47	55.3
Total	85	100

Table 1 shows the number of respondents/students used for the survey according to gender. A total of 38 (44.7%) are male while 47 (55.3%) of the respondents are female.

Research Question: Do the students have access to online facilities for teaching Computer Studies?

Table 2 Online facilities usage for teaching

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	1.00	3	3.5	3.5
Disagree	2.00	5	5.9	9.4
Neutral	3.00	14	16.5	25.9
Agree	4.00	38	44.7	70.6
Strongly Agree	5.00	25	29.4	100.0
Total		85	100.0	100.0

Table 2 shows the frequency table for online facilities usage for teaching. 3.5% of the respondents strongly disagree that they have regular access to online course materials (e.g., lesson notes, slides) for Computer Studies. 5.9% disagreed, 16.5% respondents were neutral, 44.7% agreed and 29.4% strongly agreed that they have regular access to online facilities for Computer Studies. This shows that 74.1% of the respondents have access to online facilities for teaching Computer Studies.

Table 3 Study Habits in Computer Studies

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	1.00	4	4.7	4.7	4.7
Disagree	2.00	4	4.7	4.7	9.4
Neutral	3.00	15	17.7	17.7	27.1
Agree	4.00	34	40.0	40.0	67.1
Strongly Agree	5.00	28	32.9	32.9	100.0
	Total	85	100.0	100.0	

Table 3 shows the frequency of study habits of secondary students in Computer Studies with respect to online facilities usage. 9.4% of the respondents disagree that online facilities positively influence their study habits. 27.1% are neutral while 72.9% agree that the use of online facilities positively influence their study habits in Computer Studies. This shows that 72.9% of the respondents are positively influenced by online facilities in Computer Studies.

4.1. Testing Hypothesis

- H₀: There is no significant influence of online facilities for teaching on students study habits in Computer Studies.

Table 4 Pearson Correlation Coefficient of Online facilities usage for teaching and Students' Study Habits in Computer Studies

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r cal	p
Online facilities	85	3.91	1.01	0.061	0.58
Study habits	85	4.12	0.76		

Table 4 revealed the relationship between online facilities usage and study habits. The result shows that p-value (0.58) is greater than α (0.05). This revealed a weak relationship between online facilities usage for teaching and students' study habits. So, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in students study habits in relation to online facilities usage was not rejected. It means there was no significant influence in the use of online facilities for teaching and students' study habits in Computer Studies in Secondary Schools.

5. Discussion

This study investigated the influence of online facilities on students' study habits in Computer Studies. Based on the findings of the study, it was clear that students have access to online facilities for teaching and learning Computer Studies in secondary schools. 74.1% of the respondents agreed to have access to online facilities for teaching Computer Studies.

The findings of the study further revealed that there was no significant influence of online facilities usage for teaching on students' study habits in Computer Studies. This result suggested that online facilities for teaching have no significant influence on students' study habits in Computer Studies. This finding contradicts the finding of Joshi & Sharma (2017) who examined the effect of internet usage on study habits of senior secondary students and found that internet nonusers have better study habits than the students who use the internet. It agrees with the finding of Jazeel (2016) who indicated that the study habits of the internet users and non-users differed significantly and non-users of the internet were found

to be better than internet users. This finding might be due to the fact that most students were yet to familiarize themselves with the use of online facilities for learning

6. Conclusion

This study established that there was no influence of online facilities usage for teaching on students' study habits in Computer Studies. This finding contradicts previous research, which suggested a positive relationship between online facility usage and study habits. Further research is needed to explore the factors that contribute to the lack of significance in this study.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, it was therefore recommended that students should continue to employ any method and facility that is suitable for their study habits.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Aina, O. A. Poor Reading Habits Among Nigerian: The Role of Libraries, *Library Philosophy Practice*, 2011,1(45), 20-23.
- [2] Emeka, U. J. & Nyeche O. S. Impact of Internet Usage on the Academic Performance of Undergraduate Students: A Case Study of the University of Abuja, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific and Engineering Research*, 2016, 7 (10).
- [3] Jazeel, A. Differential influence of internet on learning habits of secondary school students in Ampara District of Sri Lanka. *International Engineering and Technological Applied Research Journal*, 2016,1 (2).
- [4] Joshi, P. & Sharma, S. . The Effect of Using Internet on Study Habits of Senior Secondary Students. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 2017, 5 (6).
- [5] Nneji, I. Study Habits of Nigerian University Students in Quality Conversations," *Proceedings of the 25th HEROSA*, July, 2002.
- [6] Ogungbe, O.M. An Investigation into the Reading and Studying Habits among Secondary School Students," *Journal of Science and Movement Education*, 2005, 5, 33-41.
- [7] Ogunjobi, M.O. & Ogungbe, O.M. A Study on the Influence of the Usage of Contemporary Internet and Internet Facilities on Learning Habits of Nigerian College and University Students. *International Journal of Management and Applied Science*, ISSN: 2394-7926, 2016, 6(2).
- [8] Osuchukwu, N. & Nebolise, N. Women in Adult Education Program for Sustainable Development: Challenges and Implications for Library and Information Services, 2019.
- [9] Singh, R. & Sharma, R. A Review of the Relation of Study Habits to the Academic Achievement of Students . *International Journal for Research Trends and Innovation*, 2022, 4(7) Retrieved from <https://www.ijrti.org/papers/IJRTI2204004.pdf> on March 31, 2025.
- [10] Usman, M.O., Akinpelu, B., Akindoju, O. G. , Fasinro, K.S. Onowugbed, F.U. & Abanum, C.I. Evaluating Gender Attitude Towards Learning Commerce via Web-Based Instructional Application. *Educational Perspectives*, 2024, 13(1), 72-81.